

**MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS AND FREQUENCY OF
DUDE ULCER DISEASE IN RETIREMENT PATIENTS WITH METABOLIC
SYNDROME**

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Relevance of the topic: in recent years, as a result of sudden changes in the climate in our country, the appearance of certain diseases in the human body has been sharply observed. As a result, it is clearly seen that duodenal disease, which is similar to other diseases, occurs in chronic and acute patients at the age of retirement. As a result of this, our older patients are treating 12-finger ulcer disease as a co-morbidity by means of treatments.

The purpose of the work: the purpose of the work was to determine the pathological changes in the duodenum of elderly patients with metabolic syndrome.

The results obtained: within the scope of scientific research, most of the patients with metabolic syndrome were 60-70% women of retirement age, and it was found that 12-finger intestinal ulcer disease was considered as a chronic disease.

In the course of research, macropreparations of duodenal ulcers brought to the Bureau of Pathological Anatomy were histologically examined, and it was found that the histopreparations often contain chronic hypoxia, a violation of the integrity of the mucous membrane. It was also found that most of the patients had gastric gastritis as a co-morbidity during the procedure.

Conclusions: in conclusion, it can be said that there is an ulcer in the bulbous, antral, body, small curvature, cardiac part of the stomach from the complicated ulcer of duodenal ulcer, which is common in women.

References:

1. Artikova D. O., Ruzmetova D. T. XORAZM VILOYATIDA
HOMILADOR

AYOLLARDA SIYDIK YO 'LLARI INFEKSIYASINI KECHISHI VA UNGA
OLIB KELUVCHI OMILLAR //INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND
EDUCATION. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1. – C. 3-4.

FAN, TA'LIM, TEXNOLOGIYA VA ISHLAB CHIQRARISH INTEGRATSIYASI ASOSIDA RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI

2. Bekchanov A. J. et al. Causes of death in infants born to women affected by Covid-19 disease // *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences* (2993-2149). – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 5. – С. 34-38.
3. Khasanovich K. R., Tulibaevna R. D., Ziyaevich T. H. DISTRIBUTION OF PERINATAL DISEASE IN NEWBORN CHILDREN IN KHORZAM PROVINCE BY CITY AND DISTRICT AND CAUSES OF DEATH // *World Bulletin of Public Health*. – 2021. – Т. 5. – С. 82-85.
4. Каримов Р., Авезов М. Оценка перинатальных случаев смерти, уровня и состояния заболеваний уха, горла и носа // *Журнал вестник врача*. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 60-63.
5. Karimov R. X., Tursunov X. Z., Ruzmetova D. T. Modern approaches to perinatal disease in diabetes in pregnant women // *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*. – 2021. – Т. 11. – №. 12. – С. 173-179.
6. Karimov R. X, & Musaev U. M. (2023). ANALYSIS OF RESEARCH AND COMMISSION FORENSIC EXPERTISES CONDUCTED ON LIVING PERSONS. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences* (2993-2149), 1(5), 61–63. Retrieved from <http://grnjournal.us/index.php/AJPMHS/article/view/423>
7. Каримов Р. Х., Мусаев У. М., Рузметова Д. Т. ЯТРОГЕНИЯ НА ПРИМЕРАХ ИЗ ПРАКТИКИ (По данным лет обзор) // *International conference on multidisciplinary science*. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 10-12.
8. Каримов, Р. Х., Мусаев, У. М., Рузметова, Д. Т., & Султанов, Б. Б. (2023, October). ЯТРОГЕНИЯ В НЕОНАТОЛОГИИ (ПО ДАННЫМ ЛЕТ. ОБЗОР). In *International conference on multidisciplinary science* (Vol. 1, No. 3, pp. 76-78).
9. Каримов Р. Х. и др. ВРАЧЕБНЫЕ ОШИБКИ В ПРАКТИКЕ АКУШЕРОВ-ГИНЕКОЛОГОВ // *Past and Future of Medicine: International Scientific and Practical Conference*. – 2023. – Т. 2. – С. 114-117.

FAN, TA'LIM, TEXNOLOGIYA VA ISHLAB CHIQRISH INTEGRATSIYASI ASOSIDA RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI

10. Kh K. R. et al. PATHOMORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF RESPIRATORY AIRCRAFT CHANGES IN INFANTS BORN FROM MOTHERS WITH COVID-19 //JOURNAL OF HEALTHCARE AND LIFE-SCIENCE RESEARCH. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 8. – С. 21-28.
11. Матякубова С., Рузметова Д. Особенности клинического течения при преждевременном излитии околоплодных вод и принципы ведения беременных //Журнал проблемы биологии и медицины. – 2019. – №. 1 (107). – С. 175-177.
12. Матякубова С., Рузметова Д. Фоновые факторы, влияющие на течение беременности и её исход при преждевременных разрывах плодных оболочек //Журнал проблемы биологии и медицины. – 2018. – №. 4 (104). – С. 203-205.
13. Ruzmetova D. T., Matyakubova S. A. CLINICAL PRACTICAL ASSESSMENT APPLICATION OF POLYMERASE CHAIN REACTION AS A TEST FOR ASSESSING MICROBIOCINOSIS IN PREGNANT WOMEN //Central Asian Journal of Pediatrics. – 2021. – Т. 2021. – №. 1. – С. 37-49.
14. Ruzmetova D. T., Matyakubova S. A. OCCURRENCE OF UTERINE MYOMA IN WOMEN OF REPRODUCTIVE AGE IN KHOREZM REGION //Open Access Repository. – 2023. – Т. 4. – №. 3. – С. 489-492.
15. SA M., DT R. RISK FACTORS OF DEVELOPMENT OF PRETERM PREMATURE RUPTURE OF FETAL MEMBRANES IN PREGNANT WOMEN //European Science Review. – 2018. – Т. 1.
16. Sabirjanovich Y. B. et al. ETHERIOLOGICAL FACTORS OF DEATH IN PNEUMONIAS FOUND IN NEWBORNS //EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 8. – С. 1-4.
17. Юлдашев, Б. С., Каримов, Р. Х., & Бекчанов, А. Ж. (2023, July). COVID-ўтказган оналардан туғилган чақалоқларда пневмония касаллигининг асоратлари. In *Past and Future of Medicine: International Scientific and Practical Conference* (Vol. 2, pp. 10-12).
18. Юлдашев, Б. С., Каримов, Р. Х., & Джуманиязова, Н. С. (2024). COVID-

FAN, TA'LIM, TEXNOLOGIYA VA ISHLAB CHIQRARISH INTEGRATSIYASI ASOSIDA RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI

19 ЎТКАЗГАН ЧАҚАЛОҚЛАРДА ЛИМФА ТУГУНЛАРИНИНГ МОРФОЛОГИК ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ (ХОРАЗМ ВИЛОЯТИ ПАТОЛОГИК АНАТОМИЯ ЭКСПЕРТИЗА БЮРОСИ, ХОРАЗМ ВИЛОЯТ ПЕРИНАТАЛ МАРКАЗИ). *Молодые ученые*, 2(3), 15-16.

19. Tulibayevna R. D. Characteristics of Urogenital Tract Microbiota During Pregnancy //Research Journal of Trauma and Disability Studies. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 10. – С. 249-254.

20. Юлдашев, Б. С., Каримов, Р. Х., & Джуманиязова, Н. С. (2024). ПАНДЕМИЯ ДАВРИДА ПНЕВМОНИЯ КАСАЛЛИГИ БИЛАН КАСАЛЛАНГАН ЧАҚАЛОҚЛАРДА ЛИМФА ТУГУНЛАРИНИНГ МОРФОЛОГИК ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ ЎЛИМ САБАБЛАРИ. *AMALIY VA TIBBIYOT FANLARI ILMIY JURNALI*, 3(1), 197-201.

21. Юлдашев Б. С., Каримов Р. Х., Бекчанов А. Ж. COVID-19 ЎТКАЗГАН ЧАҚАЛОҚЛАРДА ПНЕВМОНИЯНИНГ МОРФОЛОГИК ХУСУСИЯТИ //International Scientific and Practical Conference of Students and Young Scientists" Sustainable Development: Problems, Analysis, Prospects"(Poland). – 2023. – С. 26-28.

22. Yuldashev B. S. et al. Causes of Pneumonia In Infants Born of Mothers Infected With Covid-19 //International Journal of Integrative and Modern Medicine. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 9-16.

23. Yuldashev, B. S., Kuruyazov, A. Q., Khodzhimuratov, O., & Karimov, R. X. (2023). OCCURRENCE OF CLINICAL PALATE AND LIP DEFECT WITH FACIAL ANOMALIES IN KHORAZM REGION. *International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research*, 3(11), 80-85.

24. Kuryazov Akbar Quranbaevich, Karimov Rasulbek Khasanovich, Ruzmetova Dilfuza Tulibaevna, & Bobojanov Yoldoshboy Bakhtiyor o'g'li. (2024). PREVENTION OF PERIODONTITIS DISEASE IN MIDDLE-AGED WOMEN. INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON MEDICINE, SCIENCE, AND EDUCATION, 1(1), 271–274. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10599587>

25. Yuldashev, B. S., Kuruyazov, A. Q., Khodzhimuratov, O., & Karimov, R. X.

FAN, TA'LIM, TEXNOLOGIYA VA ISHLAB CHIQRARISH INTEGRATSIYASI ASOSIDA RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI

(2023). A CASE OF LIP DEFECT WITH FACIAL ANOMALIES IN KHORAZM REGION. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences* (2993-2149), 1(9), 547-552.

26. Sabirjanevich, Y. B., Khasanovich, K. R., Tulibaevna, R. D., & Safarboevich, R. S. (2024). RATE OF GLAUCOMA IN PENSION AGE CITIZENS (2023 in the example of the city of Urganch). *International Journal of Alternative and Contemporary Therapy*, 2(1), 4-7.

27. Sabirjanevich, Y. B., Khasanovich, K. R., & Safarboevich, R. S. (2024). RELATIONSHIP OF OTHER TYPES OF DISEASES WITH EYE DISEASES. *МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА*, 2(1), 29-35.

28. Юлдашев, Б. С., Исмаилов, О., Каримов, Р. Х., & Исмаилов, О. (2023). Хомила ва янги туғилган чақалоқлар мурдасининг суд тиббий экспертизаси (Текшируви). *Ўқув қўлланма: Т.: "О 'ZKITOBSAVDONASHRIYOTI" NMIU*, 96.

29. Сатликов, Р. К., Юлдашев, Б. С., Закиров, Ш. Ю., Каримов, Р. Х., & ИЗУЧЕНИЯ, М. (2022). ИНФЕКЦИЯХ МОЧЕВЫХ ПУТЕЙ. *Монография:-Т.: "О 'ZKITOBSAVDONASHRIYOTI" NMIU*, 84.

30. Турсунов, Х. З., Каримов, Р. Х., Сапаев, Д. Ш., & Сапаев, М. Ф. (2022). Буйрак ва буйрак усти беги касаллиги, уни даволаш усуллари ҳамда асоратлари (адабиётлар шарҳи).

31. Qurbanbaevich, K. A., Khasanovich, K. R., & Tulibaevna, R. D. (2024, February). CARIES DISEASE IN YOUNG CHILDREN. In *International conference on multidisciplinary science* (Vol. 2, No. 2, pp. 35-37).

32. Юлдашев, Б. С., Ходжаниязов, А. А., Каримов, Р. Х., & Жуманиязова, Н. С. (2024). ЧАСТОТА МЕТАСТАЗИРУЮЩЕГО РАКА МОЛОЧНОЙ ЖЕЛЕЗЫ В ЗАВИСИМОСТИ ОТ ВОЗРАСТА. *Yangi O'zbekistonda Tabiiy va Ijtimoiy-gumanitar fanlar respublika ilmiy amaliy konferensiyasi*, 2(2), 141-143.

33. Sabirjanevich, Y. B., Khasanovich, K. R., Tulibaevna, R. D., Safarboevich, R. S., & Azamatovich, K. A. (2024). DYNAMICS OF ANTHROPOMETRIC INDICATORS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF ONE-YEAR-OLD CHILDREN. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences* (2993-2149), 2(2), 560-563.

34. Sobirjanevich, Y. B., Alievich, M. A., & Xasanovich, K. R. (2024). Этиология Гепатоцеллюлярной Карциномы: Особое Внимание Жировой Болезни Печени. *Research Journal of Trauma and Disability Studies*, 3(3), 26-36.

FAN, TA'LIM, TEXNOLOGIYA VA ISHLAB CHIQRARISH INTEGRATSIYASI ASOSIDA RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI

35. Рузматов, П. Ю., Матмуротов, К. Ж., Бабаджанов, А. Р., Каримов, Р. Х., & Рузметов, Б. А. (2024). ОСОБЕННОСТИ ВЫПОЛНЕНИЯ РЕКОНСТРУКТИВНЫХ ВМЕШАТЕЛЬСТВ У БОЛЬНЫХ СИНДРОМОМ ДИАБЕТИЧЕСКОЙ СТОПЫ. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 2(3), 96-112.

36. Sabirzhanevich, Y. B., Khasanovich, K. R., Tulibaevna, R. D., Zhumabaevich, K. U., Farkhadovich, A. A., Azamatovich, K. A., ... & Alisherovich, K. D. (2024). PREGNANCY PLANNING FOR WOMEN WITH TYPE 2 DIABETES IN NUKUS CITY (2022-2023). *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(3), 233-241.

37. Abdullayev, O. (2024). XORAZM VILOYATIDA GEPATIT S KASALLIGINING TARQALISHI. AMALIY VA TIBBIYOT FANLARI ILMIY JURNALI, 3(3), 189-196.

38. Sabirzhanevich, Y. B., Jumabaevich, K. U., Khasanovich, K. R., Tulibievna, R. D., Azamatovich, K. A., & Dilshadovich, J. D. (2024). PATHOLOGICAL OCCURRENCE AND COMPLICATIONS OF THE DIABETIC TOPIC SYNDROME IN PATIENTS WITH TYPE 2 DIABETES DISEASE WHO APPLY TO THE OUTPATIENT. *Research Journal of Trauma and Disability Studies*, 3(3), 219-227.

39. Matyakubova, S. A., & Ruzmetova, D. T. (2018). Risk factors of development of preterm premature rupture of fetal membranes in pregnant women. *European science review*, (9-10-2), 96-97.

40. Sabirzhanevich, Y. B., Jumabaevich, K. U., Khasanovich, K. R., Tulibievna, R. D., & Raimberganovna, M. F. (2024, March). STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF PATIENTS WITH DIABETES 2 DISEASE (in the example of the city of Nukus in 2023). In *International conference on multidisciplinary science* (Vol. 2, No. 3, pp. 162-165).

41. Юлдашев, Б. С., Каримов, Р. Х., Мадаминов, Ф. А., & Мадаминов, А. С. (2024). СНИЖЕНИЕ ЧАСТОТЫ РАЗВИТИЯ НОЗОКОМИАЛЬНОЙ ИНФЕКЦИИ МОЧЕВОГО ТРАКТА ПРИ СОЧЕТАНИИ АНТИБИОТИКОВ С ИММУНОМОДУЛЯТОРАМИ. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences*, 3(12), 107-109.

42. Karimov Rasulbek Khasanovich, Rakhimbaev Makhmud Davlatbaevich, & Radjarov Adilbek Anvarbekovich. (2024). MORPHOLOGY AND HISTOCHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF BRAIN TISSUE IN ACUTE INTOXICATION PSYCHOSIS. *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON MEDICINE*,

FAN, TA'LIM, TEXNOLOGIYA VA ISHLAB CHIQRARISH INTEGRATSIYASI ASOSIDA RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI

SCIENCE, AND EDUCATION, 1(7), 49–54. Retrieved from <https://universalconference.us/universalconference/index.php/icmse/article/view/2282>

43. Karimov Rasulbek Khasanovich, Musaeva Iroda Mansurbekovna, & Radjapov Adilbek Anvarbekovich. (2024). MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF TWELVE FINGER ULCER DISEASE. *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE OF NATURAL AND SOCIAL-HUMANITARIAN SCIENCES*, 1(6), 26–31. Retrieved from

<https://universalconference.us/universalconference/index.php/ICNSHS/article/view/2297>